

Supplementary Material: Fixed-Order H-Infinity Controller Design for Port-Hamiltonian Systems

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We report additional experimental data for all passive plants from the Complib-Library [4]. The results are presented in Figure 1, Figure 2, and Figure 3. In all comparisons we can observe, that the three controller synthesis methods lead to a similar \mathcal{H}_∞ performance but after applying a passivity-enforcing post-processing step as described in [3] the \mathcal{H}_∞ performance of the conventional fixed-order methods HIFOO [2] and `hinfstruct` [1] sometimes deteriorates drastically. Note that a passivity-enforcing post-processing step is not necessary when using SOBSYN, since SOBSYN controllers are designed to be port-Hamiltonian and thus passive.

Figure 1: Experimental data for the DLR1, LAH, and NN18 plants

Figure 2: Experimental data for the plants EB1, EB2, EB3, and EB4

Figure 3: Experimental data for the plants EB5 and EB6

References

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